

Planar broadband antenna for 2G/3G systems

Ashutosh Singh Chauhan¹, Priyansh Kasyap¹, Ankit Gupta¹, Debani Prasad Mishra¹,
Surender Reddy Salkuti², Seong-Cheol Kim²

¹Department of Electronics and Telecommunications Engineering, International Institute of Information Technology (IIIT)
Bhubaneswar, Bhubaneswar, Odisha 751029, India

²Department of Railroad and Electrical Engineering, Woosong University, Daejeon 34606, Republic of Korea

Article Info

Article history:

Received Dec 10, 2020

Revised Apr 12, 2022

Accepted Apr 20, 2022

Keywords:

2G/3G

CST microwave studio

Dipole antenna

Microstrip antenna

Mobile communication

ABSTRACT

A planar antenna with broadband gestalt is presented for mobile networks. The structure of the antenna is made up of a folded dipole pair with an L-figure microstrip coupling line. The microstrip coupling along with the dipoles are attached on a similar substrate. The radiation parts are plotted at 1.7 GHz, 2.2 GHz, and 2.7 GHz. A flexible coaxial cable made of perfect electric conductor (PEC) material is attached to the L-figure microstrip whereas the outside conductor made up of RO4350B material is attached to the coplanar strip of line. The gain of the antenna is almost 9 dBi. The benefit of the planar structure is that it offers a simple feeding structure and compact size that is necessary for second generation (2G)/third-generation (3G)/long-term evolution (LTE) systems. Finally, the antenna proposed is designed by using computer simulation technology (CST) microwave studio.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Surender Reddy Salkuti

Department of Railroad and Electrical Engineering, Woosong University

17-2, Jayang-Dong, Dong-Gu, Daejeon - 34606, Republic of Korea

Email: surender@wsu.ac.kr

1. INTRODUCTION

The brisk advancement in the mobile communication field requires broadband and cheaper antennas. Of the different generations, the second generation (2G), like the GSM1800, can be operated in ranges from 1700 MHz to 1880 MHz and 1850 MHz to 2000 MHz. Wideband code division multiple access (WCDMA) and code division multiple access-2000 (CDMA-2000) are third-generation (3G) communication systems that operate in the frequency range of 1920 MHz to 2180 MHz. Long-term evolution (LTE), like the LTE2500 and LTE2300, have frequency ranges of 2500 Mhz to 2690 MHz and 2300 MHz to 2400 MHz respectively. Hence the essential bandwidth is 45% i.e., 1.65 GHz to 2.75 GHz for antennas working in the base station 2G/3G/LTE mode [1], [2]. Hence modern antennas applicable for mobile communication purposes must be capable of covering all the required frequency bands.

In the recent past, different types of planar antennas and their properties have been researched and evolved for broadband stations. Most frequently used are dipole and patch antennas because of their directional properties and sizes, also patch antennas have a narrower bandwidth [3]. An L-shaped probe has been used as it enhances the bandwidth. L-shaped antennas provide bandwidths of approximately 28% at return loss greater than 10 dB. Similarly, bowtie-shaped metal patch antenna attains bandwidth of approximately 44% (return loss (RL) > 10 dB) but parallelly surfaces with higher impedance are also required [4]. Printed dipoles on the lower side along with the balun and proper impedance matching are proposed to achieve higher bandwidth. Adjusted balun and the printed dipole in [5] reached a bandwidth of 40% (RL > 10 dB). The double-layered structure as given in [6] integrated along with dipoles attains a bandwidth of 50% (RL > 10 dB), but the antenna gain substantially drops. All the dipole configurations

discussed have a nonplanar structure. Different slot cuts, their positions, and configurations determine the bandwidth and directivity of antennas, and a suitable shape is arrived at after analyzing the requirements and comparing it with the results obtained.

The antenna designed in [7] has four radiators that are looped and fed using a Y-shaped line and attains a higher bandwidth at higher frequencies nearing 2.7 GHz but the antenna fails to extend to lower frequency ranges for 2G applications. The design mentioned in [8], [9] consists of printed dipoles that are double-sided and series fed and attain a bandwidth of approximately 20% at 1.6 GHz but at the same time antenna operation is constrained in the upper segment with a constant bandwidth of 25% at 1.5 GHz. A novel design has been developed and applied in [10]-[12] and has a pair of folded dipoles that operate efficiently in a frequency range of 1.65 GHz to 2.7 GHz. However, the antenna is limited only to array applications which makes it difficult to be redesigned or reconfigured for various applications primarily because of its rigid geometry and necessary pairing of printed dipoles and its counterparts [13].

This paper presents a versatile and compact antenna that has been proposed for the broadband applications of 2G/3G mobile communication. The designed antenna comprises paired dipoles, folded, which are linked parallel to a coplanar strip. The L-shaped microstrip lines on top of the antenna are used to feed the folded dipoles, which are present on the lower side of the substrate. A 50 Ω coaxial cable is used for feeding purposes whose inner conductor is linked to the L-shaped microstrip and the outer cover is linked to a coplanar stripline. The motivation behind the work is:

- The advantage of the 3G network is that it can cover immense territory with relatively few cells. This is because the network does not require as much bandwidth and therefore requires fewer cells.
- With the advancement of fifth generation (5G) technology, overcrowding of signals due to increased bandwidth is causing the problem. Therefore, it is necessary to work on 2G/3G technology to decrease overcrowding.
- New technology like 5G requires new configuration, therefore, forcing users to buy new hardware to support the new technology. It has become important to work on existing technology to decrease costs for users.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

To satisfy features like low-cost, simple manufacturing, and integration of systems it is preferable that antennas for base stations should have lightweight and planar structure. To obtain high bandwidth along with better isolation, the feeding structures proposed were complex which resulted in a nonplanar configuration. Characteristics that determine impedance matching in planar antennas are slot width of the coplanar strip, length of the coupling microstrip line, and also the distance of the antenna from the reflector known as height [14], [15]. The design of the broadband planar antenna in computer simulation technology (CST) Microwave Studio is divided into the designs of the following subparts of the antenna.

2.1. Substrate

The substrate of the antenna was presented as being connected through a coat of copper of dielectric substance Rogers RO4350B with the help of CST software. The relative dielectric value is 3.48. The loss tangent of the dielectric is 0.0037 and the width is 0.76 mm [16].

2.2. Pair of folded dipoles

The structure of the planar antenna comprises a pair of folded dipoles attached parallelly to a coplanar stripline. The dipoles shown in Figure 1 are attached to the lower face of the substrate. Figure 1(a) depicts the dimensions of folded dipoles, and Figure 1(b) shows the pair of folded dipoles on the lower part of the antenna. They are made up of material copper (annealed). The length and breadth are 53.68 mm and 25.75 mm respectively. The slot width (Wd) of the gap between the two folded dipoles is a crucial thing for matching impedance. The most suitable value for (Wd) is found to be around 2.10 mm for the optimum matching of impedance [11], [17].

2.3. L-shaped microstrip

At the top face of the substrate, the L-shaped microstrip line is present whose dimensions are shown in Figure 2. Patch antennas along with L-shaped probes were suggested for enhancement of bandwidth [18]. With the use of coupling microstrip lines, an improvement in impedance matching can be obtained. The dipoles on the lower face are connected by this L-shaped microstrip [19]-[21].

Figure 1. Folded dipoles: (a) dimensions of folded dipoles and (b) pair of folded dipoles on the lower part of the antenna

Figure 2. Dimensions of L-strip microstripline

2.4. Reflector

An antenna reflector is a gadget that bounces back electromagnetic waves. Antenna reflectors act as a device for transmitting radio frequency (RF) energy or can be made as part of an antenna structure. Here the reflector as shown in Figure 3 is integrated into the antenna, as it serves to change the radiating pattern of the antenna, modifying gain in a specific direction. Figure 3(a) shows the reflector at a distance H from the antenna, and Figure 3(b) shows the bottom view of reflector. Without the reflector, the matching of impedance is not good (i.e., $H = \infty$). When the reflector is used, the matching of impedance is enhanced. But care is needed, not to get the antenna too close to the reflector as the impedance matching starts deteriorating after a certain distance, hence the best results were found at $H = 42$ mm [22]-[24].

Figure 3. Design of reflector: (a) at a distance H from the antenna and (b) bottom view of reflector

2.5. Microstrip patch antenna (MPA) feed line and impedance matching

A feedline has the purpose to excite to transfer by direct or indirect contact. There are varieties of different ways of feeding and we have applied microstrip feed. Here, we have used the coaxial probe as shown in Figure 4 for feeding purposes, the outer conducting part of the probe is made of Rogers RO4350B material

and the inner conducting part is made of perfect electric conductor (PEC) material [25], [26]. Figure 4(a) shows the outer cover of coaxial probe, Figure 4(b) shows the inner conductor of coaxial probe, and Figure 4(c) shows the feed part of the coaxial cable. The inside conductor of the $50\ \Omega$ coaxial probe is connected to the L-shaped microstrip and the outer covering of the wire is connected to the coplanar strip along with the antenna. The radius of the inner conducting part is 0.416 mm and the radius of the outer conductor is 1.8 mm [27], [28]. Advantages of coaxial feed are can be fabricated with ease, impedance matching can be done, and low spurious radiation.

Figure 4. Coaxial probe: (a) outer cover, (b) inner conductor, and (c) feed part of the coaxial cable

2.6. Determination of feed point

After determining the feed type with specified parameters, the matching impedance was aimed to be as close to $50\ \Omega$. The connector has to be attached at some distance to balance the impedance. To get the least quantity of the return loss hit and trial method was used [29]-[32].

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Using the CST Microwave Studio, we have simulated the antenna. Various parameters of the antenna are analyzed such as S-parameter which shows how much energy is transferred back and tried to keep it minimum; Impedance matching so that the desired signal can be emitted without any back transfer. We have analyzed the reflection coefficient and tried to keep it below 8 dB as per our requirement. The transmission coefficient at 1.5 GHz, 2.5 GHz, is -8 dB, -14 dB respectively. Furthermore, different parameters like voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR), Fairfield, S-parameter, directivity have been properly demonstrated.

3.1. S-parameter

The input and output combinations between terminals in an antenna are represented by an S-parameter. It is called a reflection coefficient as it shows how much energy per unit time is reflected and is denoted by $S_{1,1}$ and also called return loss. For impedance equalization, the slot width of the stripped line is a principal parameter. Figure 5 depicts the results for varying return loss of the antenna with varying slot width (Wd). We get the best impedance matching by keeping Wd to 2.1 mm.

Figure 5. Return loss vs frequency plot where $S_{1,1}(1)-Wd = 1.5\ \text{mm}$, $S_{1,1}(2)-Wd = 2.7\ \text{mm}$, $S_{1,1}(3)-Wd = 2.1\ \text{mm}$

Impedance matching is also changed by the distance of the antenna from the reflector, known as H. Figure 6 depicts the dependence of height on return loss of the antenna. The impedance matching quality lowers when the antenna moves towards the reflector and also degrades when placed too far away from the antenna. The best results are at a height of 42 mm.

Figure 6. Return loss vs frequency plot where $S_{1,1}(3)\text{-H} = 42$ mm, $S_{1,1}(4)\text{-H} = 32$ mm, $S_{1,1}(5)\text{-H} = 52$ mm

3.2. VSWR

VSWR shows a comparison of how well the energy per unit time is transferred along the transmission line of the point of load. A matched antenna has less reflection coefficient as well as a low value of VSWR. Figure 7 depicts the results obtained for VSWR in the required frequency range.

Figure 7. VSWR vs frequency plot

3.3. Directivity

It is a parameter that shows the degree to which the radiation is shown in a particular direction. Figure 8 depicts the radiation pattern obtained at 1.65, 2.25, and 2.75 GHz. The observed range of frequency is from 1.65 to 2.75 GHz to demonstrate and analyze radiation, directivity over the frequency range of operation. Figure 8(a) shows the radiation pattern at a frequency of 1.65 GHz and $\Phi = 0$, Figure 8(b) shows the radiation pattern at a frequency of 1.65 GHz and $\Phi = 90$, Figure 8(c) shows the radiation pattern at a frequency of 2.25 GHz and $\Phi = 0$. Figure 8(d) shows the radiation pattern at a frequency of 2.25 GHz and $\Phi = 90$, Figure 8(e) shows the radiation pattern at a frequency of 2.75 GHz and $\Phi = 0$, and Figure 8(f) shows the radiation pattern at a frequency of 2.75 GHz and $\Phi = 90$.

From the above radiation patterns, it can be observed that at 1.65 GHz, 2.25 GHz, and 2.75 GHz there is hardly any notable deviation in patterns of radiation ranging across a broad frequency range of operation which is desired. Figure 9 depicts the Farfield plot which presents the directivity of the antenna concerning theta and phi plane at 2.5 GHz where return loss is the least. The gain versus frequency response is observed in the next subsection.

Figure 8. Radiation patterns at frequencies: (a) 1.65 GHz, $\Phi = 0^\circ$; (b) 1.65 GHz, $\Phi = 90^\circ$; (c) 2.25 GHz, $\Phi = 0^\circ$; (d) 2.25 GHz, $\Phi = 90^\circ$; (e) 2.75 GHz, $\Phi = 0^\circ$; and (f) 2.75 GHz, $\Phi = 90^\circ$

Figure 9. Farfield plot simulated for 2.5 GHz

3.4. Gain vs frequency

A Gain of an antenna relates the amount of power that is being transmitted in direction of peak radiation to the power transmitted by an isotropic source. Figure 10 depicts the dependence of gain and frequency. The maximum gain is obtained at a frequency of 2.5 GHz. Table 1 presents the change in antenna parameters concerning the width of the coplanar stripline. From this Table 1, it can be observed that with the increase in slot width of the coplanar stripline (Wd) directivity increases but bandwidth does not increase accordingly. Hence $Wd = 2.1$ mm is the optimal value and there is compensation between directivity and bandwidth of the antenna.

Figure 10. Gain vs frequency plot

Table 1. Change in antenna parameters concerning the width of coplanar stripline

Width (Wd)	Directivity	Bandwidth
$Wd = 1.5 \text{ mm}$	10.3 dBi	306 MHz
$Wd = 2.1 \text{ mm}$	10.4 dBi	347 MHz
$Wd = 2.7 \text{ mm}$	11 dBi	248 MHz

4. CONCLUSION

A broadband planar antenna to work in the operating frequency range of 1.65 GHz to 2.75 GHz has been simulated successfully using CST Microwave Studio. The desired results were found out at $Wd = 2.1 \text{ mm}$ and $H = 42 \text{ mm}$. The proposed antenna can be used to enhance 2G/3G communication which needs to work in multiple frequency ranges and can meet the new standards of communication. The main advantages we get are its comparatively small size, better impedance matching, less reflection coefficient, more VSWR, and better directivity. Shortly, one can proceed with a similar type of framework consisting of an antenna array that can provide better gain and directivity at the same time providing better bandwidth with almost the same reflection coefficient. The disadvantage of the wide range of frequency operations is the noise factor can also be mitigated.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research work was funded by “Woosong University’s Academic Research Funding - 2022”.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Guo, K. Khoo, and L. C. Ong, “Wideband Dual-Polarized Patch Antenna With Broadband Baluns,” in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 55, no. 1, pp. 78-83, Jan. 2007, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2006.888398.
- [2] U. K. Revankar and Harishchandra, “Printed dipole radiating elements for broadband and wide scan angle active phased array,” *IEEE Antennas and Propagation Society International Symposium. 2001 Digest. Held in conjunction with: USNC/URSI National Radio Science Meeting (Cat. No.01CH37229)*, 2001, vol. 4, pp. 796-799, doi: 10.1109/APS.2001.959585.
- [3] R. Li, T. Wu, B. Pan, K. Lim, J. Laskar, and M. M. Tentzeris, “Equivalent-Circuit Analysis of a Broadband Printed Dipole with Adjusted Integrated Balun and an Array for Base Station Applications,” in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 57, no. 7, pp. 2180-2184, July 2009, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2009.2021967.
- [4] S. Shukla, V. Khare, S. Garg, and P. Sharma, “Comparative study of 1G, 2G, 3G, 4G,” *Journal of Engineering Computers and Applied Science*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 55-63, Apr. 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.403.2882&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- [5] J. Lai, B. Feng, Q. Zeng, and S. Su, “A Dual-Band Dual-Polarized Omnidirectional Antenna for 2G/3G/LTE Indoor System Applications,” *2018 IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing, Communications and Computing (ICSPCC)*, 2018, pp. 1-3, doi: 10.1109/ICSPCC.2018.8567727.
- [6] X. -W. Dai, Z. -Y. Wang, C. -H. Liang, X. Chen, and L. -T. Wang, “Multiband and Dual-Polarized Omnidirectional Antenna for 2G/3G/LTE Application,” in *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 12, pp. 1492-1495, 2013, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2013.2289743.
- [7] K. Kumaravel, “Comparative study of 3G and 4G in mobile technology,” *International Journal of Computer Science Issues*, vol. 8, no. 5, Sep. 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.403.3451&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- [8] B. Feng, K. L. Chung, J. Lai, and Q. Zeng, “A Conformal Magneto-Electric Dipole Antenna With Wide H-Plane and Band-Notch Radiation Characteristics for Sub-6-GHz 5G Base-Station,” in *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 17469-17479, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2896356.
- [9] Y. Cui, L. Wu and R. Li, “Bandwidth Enhancement of a Broadband Dual-Polarized Antenna for 2G/3G/4G and IMT Base Stations,” in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 66, no. 12, pp. 7368-7373, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2018.2867046.
- [10] Y. Li, C. -Y. -D. Sim, Y. Luo, and G. Yang, “12-Port 5G Massive MIMO Antenna Array in Sub-6GHz Mobile Handset for LTE Bands 42/43/46 Applications,” in *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 344-354, 2018, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2763161.
- [11] Y. Qin, R. Li, and Y. Cui, “Embeddable Structure for Reducing Mutual Coupling in Massive MIMO Antennas,” in *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 195102-195112, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3033717.
- [12] N. I. A. Ishak, N. Seman, and T. H. Chua, “Antenna array design with rectangular ring slot for 5G technology,” *TELKOMNIKA (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 2258-2267, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.12928/TELKOMNIKA.v17i5.12816.
- [13] C. -Y. -D. Sim, C. -C. Chang, and J. -S Row, “Dual-feed dual-polarized patch antenna with low cross polarization and high isolation,” *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 57, no. 10, pp. 3321-3324, Oct. 2009, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2009.2028702.
- [14] Z. Zhou, S. Yang, and Z. Nie, “A Novel Broadband Printed Dipole Antenna With Low Cross-Polarization,” in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 55, no. 11, pp. 3091-3093, Nov. 2007, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2007.908570.
- [15] N. Ravikumar and J. R. Shankar, “Current and future trends in wireless mobile communication system,” *IOSR Journal of Electronics and Communication Engineering (IOSR-JECE)*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 16-20, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jece/papers/Vol.%2010%20Issue%202/Version-2/D010221620.pdf>
- [16] D. Lukić, M. Koprivica, N. Nešković, and A. Nešković, “Experimental performance analysis of THE 2G/3G/4G public mobile network,” *2016 24th Telecommunications Forum (TELFOR)*, 2016, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/TELFOR.2016.7818767.

- [17] Y. -L. Ban, Z. -X. Chen, Z. Chen, K. Kang, and J. L. -W. Li, "Decoupled Hepta-Band Antenna Array for WWAN/LTE Smartphone Applications," in *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 13, pp. 999-1002, 2014, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2014.2325877.
- [18] A. Diallo, C. Luxey, P. Le Thuc, R. Staraj, and G. Kossiavas, "Study and Reduction of the Mutual Coupling Between Two Mobile Phone PIFAs Operating in the DCS1800 and UMTS Bands," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 54, no. 11, pp. 3063-3074, Nov. 2006, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2006.883981.
- [19] O. M. Longe, "Effect of signal strength on handover in GSM networks in Owo, Ondo State, Nigeria," *3rd IEEE International Conference on Adaptive Science and Technology (ICAST 2011)*, 2011, pp. 138-143, doi: 10.1109/ICASTech.2011.6145166.
- [20] Y. S. Rao, Wing-Cheong Yeung, and A. Kripalani, "Third-generation (3G) radio access standards," *WCC 2000 - ICCT 2000. 2000 International Conference on Communication Technology Proceedings (Cat. No.00EX420)*, 2000, pp. 1017-1023 vol. 2, doi: 10.1109/ICCT.2000.890849.
- [21] P. Chitrapu and B. Aghili, "Evolution of GSM into the Next Generation Wireless World," *2007 IEEE Long Island Systems, Applications and Technology Conference*, 2007, pp. 1-10, doi: 10.1109/LISAT.2007.4312632.
- [22] S. P. Bendale and J. Rajesh Prasad, "Security Threats and Challenges in Future Mobile Wireless Networks," *2018 IEEE Global Conference on Wireless Computing and Networking (GCWCN)*, 2018, pp. 146-150, doi: 10.1109/GCWCN.2018.8668635.
- [23] C. M. H. Noblet, R. H. Owen, C. Saraiva, and N. Wahid, "Assessing the effects of GSM cell location re-use for UMTS network," *Second International Conference on 3G Mobile Communication Technologies*, 2001, pp. 82-86, doi: 10.1049/cp:20010017.
- [24] H. Xu, H. Zhou, S. Gao, H. Wang, and Y. Cheng, "Multimode Decoupling Technique With Independent Tuning Characteristic for Mobile Terminals," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 65, no. 12, pp. 6739-6751, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2017.2754445.
- [25] H. Setiawan and H. Ochi, "Study feasibility of common wireless communication services recognition for GSM, UMTS and LTE," *2009 International Conference on Advanced Technologies for Communications*, 2009, pp. 253-256, doi: 10.1109/ATC.2009.5349602.
- [26] D. Wu, S. W. Cheung, and T. I. Yuk, "A Compact and Low-Profile Loop Antenna With Multiband Operation for Ultra-Thin Smartphones," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 63, no. 6, pp. 2745-2750, June 2015, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2015.2412962.
- [27] M. A. A. E. -Ata, "Evolution of mobile cellular communication systems. The journey to UMTS," *Proceedings of the Seventeenth National Radio Science Conference. 17th NRSC'2000 (IEEE Cat. No.00EX396)*, 2000, pp. INV2/1-INV2/17, doi: 10.1109/NRSC.2000.838836.
- [28] A. Diallo, C. Luxey, P. L. Thuc, R. Staraj, and G. Kossiavas, "Enhanced two-antenna structures for universal mobile telecommunications system diversity terminals," *IET Microwaves, Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 93-101, 2008, doi: 10.1049/iet-map:20060220.
- [29] X. Wang, Z. Du, and K. Gong, "A Compact Wideband Planar Diversity Antenna Covering UMTS and 2.4 GHz WLAN Bands," in *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 7, pp. 588-591, 2008, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2008.2000664.
- [30] C. -N. Hu, K. Peng, C. -H. Yu, T. -W. Hsaio, and D. -P. Lin, "Design of a mm-wave microstrip antenna array," *2015 International Workshop on Electromagnetics: Applications and Student Innovation Competition (iWEM)*, 2015, pp. 1-2, doi: 10.1109/iWEM.2015.7365030.
- [31] D. P. Mishra, K. K. Rout, and S. R. Salkuti, "Compact MIMO antenna using dual-band for fifth-generation mobile communication system," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 921-929, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v24.i2.pp921-929.
- [32] A. Salh, L. Audah, N. S. M. Shah, and S. A. Hamzah, "Adaptive antenna selection and power allocation in downlink massive MIMO systems," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 3521-3528, 2017, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v7i6.pp3521-3528.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Ashutosh Singh Chauhan received the Bachelor of Technology (B.Tech.) degree in Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering from International Institute of Information Technology, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India in 2021. He is currently working as an Associate Software Engineer at Accenture Limited, Hyderabad. His research areas of interest include Antenna, Mobile Communication, 2G/3G Communication, Machine Learning. He can be contacted at email: b217014@iiit-bh.ac.in.

Priyansh Kasyap received the Bachelor of Technology (B.Tech.) degree in Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering from International Institute of Information Technology, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India in 2021. He is currently pursuing M.Tech in Solid State Devices from IIT Bombay. His research areas of interest include Antenna, Mobile Communication, 2G/3G Communication, VLSI. He can be contacted at email: b217029@iiit-bh.ac.in.

Ankit Gupta received the Bachelor of Technology (B.Tech.) degree in Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering from International Institute of Information Technology, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India in 2021. He is currently working as a Analyst at Deloitte USI Consulting, Hyderabad. His research areas of interest include Antenna, Mobile Communication, 2G/3G Communication, Machine Learning. He can be contacted at email: b217007@iiit-bh.ac.in.

Debani Prasad Mishra received the B.Tech. in electrical engineering from the Biju Patnaik University of Technology, Odisha, India, in 2006 and the M.Tech in power systems from IIT, Delhi, India in 2010. He has been awarded the Ph.D. degree in power systems from Veer Surendra Sai University of Technology, Odisha, India, in 2019. He is currently serving as Assistant Professor in the Dept of Electrical Engg, International Institute of Information Technology Bhubaneswar, Odisha. He has 11 years of teaching experience and 2 years of industry experience in the thermal power plant. He is the author of more than 80 research articles. His research interests include soft Computing techniques application in power system, signal processing and power quality. 3 students have been awarded Ph.D under his guidance and currently 4 Ph.D. Scholars are continuing under him. He can be contacted at email: debani@iiit-bh.ac.in.

Surender Reddy Salkuti received the Ph.D. degree in electrical engineering from the Indian Institute of Technology, New Delhi, India, in 2013. He was a Postdoctoral Researcher with Howard University, Washington, DC, USA, from 2013 to 2014. He is currently an Associate Professor with the Department of Railroad and Electrical Engineering, Woosong University, Daejeon, South Korea. His current research interests include power system restructuring issues, ancillary service pricing, real and reactive power pricing, congestion management, and market clearing, including renewable energy sources, demand response, smart grid development with integration of wind and solar photovoltaic energy sources, artificial intelligence applications in power systems, and power system analysis and optimization. He can be contacted at email: surender@wsu.ac.kr.

Seong-Cheol Kim received B.S., M.S. and Ph.D degrees, in Electronic Engineering from Korea University in 1987, 1989 and 1997, respectively. He is currently serving as Head of Railroad and Electrical Engineering Department, Woosong University, Korea. His research interests are mobile communication system and pulsed power system. He can be contacted at email: kmin@wsu.ac.kr.